

MUTUAL COOPERATION IN THE DIRECTION OF CULTURE, ECONOMY, POLITICS AND SECURITY

Leyla NAGIYEVA

Baku State University PhD Student, Baku, Azerbaijan
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0999-2838, e-mail: nleyla592@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The geopolitical changes that took place at the end of the last century, the emergence of new independent Turkish states on the political map of the world and facing the challenges of the globalized world led to the need for Turkic-speaking peoples to act more together. Since the 90s of the last century, the summit meetings of the heads of Turkic-speaking countries have played an important role in the protection and promotion of the common spiritual heritage. The holding of summit meetings of the heads of Turkic-speaking countries, the establishment of the International Organization of Turkish Culture (TURKSOY), the establishment of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States (Turkish Council), the establishment of the Parliamentary Assembly of Turkic-Speaking Countries (TÜRKPA), the Turkish Academy, the Turkish Culture and Heritage Foundation and the Turkish Business Council or the establishment of related organizations arose from this necessity. After the establishment of the mentioned institutions, the cooperation between Turkic-speaking countries has entered a new organizational stage. Thus, the heads of the Turkish states laid the foundation for systematic activities that serve to strengthen relations in political, economic, cultural and other fields, and created the foundation for the strengthening of eternal bonds of brotherhood.

Keywords: Political issue, traditional value, economy, civilization, history, improvement, government, cultural detail

INTRODUCTION

The Turkic World countries, which have been fragmented and separated from each other for centuries due to historical necessity, have found new opportunities to realize the missed opportunities with the new actions brought by globalization. Regionalization is an important part of globalization. The Turkish World has gained important opportunities to achieve new goals in accordance with modern standards of regionalization. The Turkish world is at the center of the struggle of these countries with enormous political, economic and technological capabilities. Nowadays, the Turkish Republics seem to be torn between two great powers. However, I believe that the Great Turkish race will benefit the most from globalization. Factors that predict this situation can be listed as follows:

The solid foundation on which Turkish society rests protects it well from the negative effects of globalization. Possible negative effects of globalization include the erosion of national-spiritual values, the shaking of family life, the foundation of a solid society, and the deterioration of harmful habits of man, the noble man of the earth. The Turkish nation has the ability to protect modern society from the factors that endanger it.

The new demographic conjuncture created by globalization has allowed the Turkish community to play an even more important role around the world. While population growth in the West and Russia is approaching zero point, rapid population growth and rejuvenation has begun in the Turkish world. The positive demographic factor is very effective both within the country and abroad. The spread of the Turkish population to Europe and Russia is not just the "influx" of the Turkish world. This is also to spread Turkish culture and Turkish spirit to the world and at the same

time to introduce Turkism to foreign people. On top of this, science and technology from the West were imported into the home country and adopted by the Western administration.

While the neoliberal views that form the basis of globalization ensure the significant elimination of economic borders between states, the Turkish world is getting closer to each other despite some political obstacles.

We can especially mention the importance of projects aimed at development. Mr. Ilham Aliyev's support for the development of relations between the Turkic states and the location of the headquarters of TURKPA and the Turkish Culture and Heritage Foundation in Baku is a clear example of the noted attention and care. In general, relations between Turkic-speaking countries are growing and developing day by day. Turkic-speaking people are united by common culture, traditions, national-spiritual and religious values, historical roots, and ethnic ties, and these factors are the main basis for mutually effective activity. The scope of these relations is multifaceted. TURKSOY, the International Turkish Cultural Organization, carries out an important task in the direction of protection, development and promotion of the national-spiritual heritage of the Turkic world. It is known that Turkic-speaking countries are located in an important region of the world from a geographical and strategic point of view [9, 252-257]. After TURKSOY, the establishment of the Turkic Council and TÜRKPA provides an important impetus for the comprehensive interaction of Turkic-speaking countries in the region, fights against regional security threats and helps to strengthen trade and investment opportunities [12, 24-34]. It was established based on the Nakhchivan Agreement, which was signed at the summit meeting held in Nakhchivan, one of the ancient cities of Azerbaijan, hosted by Mr. President Ilham Aliyev. Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Turkey are founding members of the organization [14]. It is no coincidence that, in 2019, the Summit meeting of the Heads of State of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States held in Azerbaijan, hosted by Mr. President Ilham Aliyev. I would like to note that in 2013 the Summit of the Heads of State was held in the city of Gabala. This can be shown as one of the clear examples of how reliable and indispensable bridge role Azerbaijan plays between Turkic-speaking countries. The Turkish Council, which is built on four main pillars such as common history, common language, common identity and common culture, does not limit itself to these commonalities. Rather, the organization intends to expand existing bilateral cooperation areas such as economy, science, education, transport, customs, tourism and other various fields among the member states to become a multilateral cooperation to benefit the region. At the same time, the organization has made important decisions on important topics such as the restoration of the historical Silk Road and the establishment of regional Turkish Diaspora centers.

TURKPA, is using the opportunities provided by the commonality of history, language and culture, plays the role of a convenient political dialogue forum for the open discussion of the common problems of the Turkish peoples and states through parliamentary diplomacy. As the first Secretary General of TURKPA, as a person who headed the Parliamentary Assembly for four years, and at the same time, as a person who was elected with the presentation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, and with the full support of other member heads of state, and as a person who served as the Secretary General of the Turkic Council for four years I can say that the tasks given by our heads of state are being successfully implemented, and in the direction of economic, political, and strategic cooperation, these fraternal organizations are the best example of turning a bilateral platform into a multilateral platform.

At the same time, organizations such as the Turkish Academy and the Turkish Culture and Heritage Foundation make great contributions to the development of science, education, and cultural-humanitarian ties between our countries.

Through these organizations, Turkic-speaking countries protect their national-moral identity and are represented as a greater power politically and economically. Therefore, the strengthening of this union has become the need of the hour. In addition to the above, the expansion of cooperation with the brotherly Turkish republics - Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan is also very important. Of course, this should be on a voluntary basis. It should be noted that Uzbekistan participated at the level of the head of state after a 20-year gap in the Summit meeting of the Heads of State of Turkic-speaking countries held in Kyrgyzstan in September of last year. It should be especially emphasized that Hungary has received observer status in the Turkic Council. Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán also participated in the Summit held in Kyrgyzstan. Already, the representatives of these countries participate in the meetings of the Turkic Council and TURKPA as observers and guests. And these activities create a favorable ground for the future participation of brotherly countries in Turkish cooperation institutions as full members. This is a clear indicator of the activity of the Turkish Council and other Turkish cooperation institutions in accordance with the recommendations and direction given by our heads of state. The preservation of stability and peace of the Turkic-speaking countries in the region, the recognition and acceptance of the territorial integrity of our countries at the level of the international relations system, among the resolutions adopted by the UN we can also emphasize issues such as the unanimous acceptance of the upcoming issues based on mutual respect among the Turkish states. Here, it is necessary to mention the issue related to the Armenia-Azerbaijan Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, that the importance of resolving the conflict as soon as possible based on the principles of the sovereignty, territorial integrity and inviolability of the internationally recognized borders of the Republic of Azerbaijan was specially emphasized in the resolutions adopted by all Summit meetings [15]. We can consider this as the success of Azerbaijan and at the same time as a contribution and solidarity given by Turkic-speaking countries to the acceptance and support of Azerbaijan's rightful voice. Turkic-speaking countries cooperate with each other in the region and develop relations with other countries in conditions of friendship and mutual understanding. Therefore, international organizations such as the Turkic Council and TURKPA among Turkic-speaking countries have always been open to other non-member countries and organizations. Our heads of state have repeatedly emphasized in their statements that all organizations and countries that are interested in mutual cooperation with us can integrate into these organizations, and in this way, satisfaction will be felt in a way that serves the common interests of each of our countries. That is why, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Hungary have joined this integration process, and we are sure that this process will continue to develop further in the future.

In addition, the above-mentioned Turkish cooperation institutions have mutually beneficial cooperation with a number of prestigious international organizations. The Turkic Council has established an excellent dialogue with the UN, the UN Development Program, the World Trade Organization, the OSCE and other influential organizations. TURKPA has been granted observer status by the Parliamentary Union of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the International Inter-Parliamentary Union, the Association of Secretaries General of International Parliaments, the Council on Interaction and Confidence Building Measures in Asia, the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization Parliamentary Assembly and the Asian Parliamentary Assembly. At the same time, the Assembly develops relations with a number of intergovernmental and interparliamentary organizations, such as the OSCE, OSCE PA, European Parliament, OIC,

GUAM, CIS PA, Baltic Assembly and CSTO Parliamentary Assembly, and participates in their activities as a guest. Within the framework of international cooperation, TURKSOY develops relations with UNESCO by carrying out joint activities related to the protection of intangible cultural heritage. Participation in other international organizations at this level creates important opportunities for Turkic-speaking countries to take a common position in the discussion of issues of their interest and support in the international arena [10, 55-59].

In addition to political relations, there are also economic relations that connect Turkic-speaking countries. It is commendable that economic relations between Turkic-speaking countries are developing every year, and trade relations are expanding. In 2017 alone, Azerbaijan's trade turnover with Turkic Council countries increased by 11.4%, and by 16% in 8 months of 2018. Mutually effective cooperation is carried out in the field of investment. 14 billion to the countries of the Turkic Council of Azerbaijan more than US dollars, and Turkic Council countries 12 billion to the economy of Azerbaijan invested more than dollars.

There are wider opportunities to further expand these economic ties, such as the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway line [11, 1-17], as well as the TANAP gas pipeline, to which other Turkic-speaking countries can be connected. In addition, the expansion of investment and online trade between the countries of the union is also considered to be an important opportunity [4, 404-417]. The bilateral trade turnover of Kazakhstan, which is sister states, with Turkey is four billion dollars. With Kyrgyzstan, this figure exceeded one billion dollars, with Azerbaijan it reached half a billion dollars.

These facts show that the overall economic strength of our countries is increasing year by year. Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan and Turkey also have space programs. At the same time, Turkic-speaking countries develop local industries by introducing new technologies and inventions to their economies [16]. Hydrocarbon pipelines, road and railway networks are being built or overhauled. The increase in the economic power of our country increases the guarantee for the success of transnational projects implemented in the region. Currently, huge economic projects implemented in the regions where our countries are located are closely connecting Europe and Asia, North and South. Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan and Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum oil and gas pipelines, which bring Caspian oil and gas to world markets, have already been put into operation. Hydrocarbon resources of Central Asia are transported to world markets through the Caspian Sea and Azerbaijan. Also, shipping between Aktau and Baku seaports is developing. The Memorandum of Understanding on Turkish sister ports signed in 2013 between the international seaports of Baku, Aktau and Samsun defines the main directions of cooperation in the field of transport for the creation of a more efficient regional transport system that combines the development plans of transport corridors and national transport plans between Turkic-speaking countries. All these projects are implemented with the aim of restoring the ancient Silk Road and further development of trade and investment cooperation within the framework of Turkish cooperation. Also, large-scale infrastructure projects are being implemented in our countries. One of the most challenging infrastructure projects is the Marmara Railway Tunnel and Suburban Mass Railway transport system. In October 2013, Mr. Recep Tayyip Erdogan, who is the Prime Minister of Turkey, opened the world's first underwater railway between two continents. The railway sections on both sides of the Bosphorus of Istanbul are connected to each other through a tunnel that passes under the Bosphorus. The project is currently one of the largest infrastructure projects in the world. With the creation of a new transport infrastructure, the Turkish world will also be connected through a transport network. The huge works done in Azerbaijan in this direction should be especially emphasized. First of all, I would

like to emphasize the importance of the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway. Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway is a historical, global project and the shortest and most reliable route connecting Europe with Asia. 5 million tons in the first stage, 17 million tons in the next stage, and more cargoes are planned to be transported through this road. After the implementation of this project, the capacity of Alat port was equal to 25 million tons of cargo and 1 million containers, which makes Alat the largest non-oil cargo port in the region. The importance of the port is also very important, the joining of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan to this project increases its importance. It should be noted that Kazakhstan is currently implementing a number of large-scale projects. An example of this is the Kazakhstan section of the West China - West Europe highway. Kazakhstan has already commissioned the Gorgas-Jetigen and West Kazakhstan-Turkmenistan border railway lines and is building a large railway line connecting Central Kazakhstan and West Kazakhstan. The Kyrgyz Republic has also started implementing transport infrastructure projects; one of them is aimed at restoring the Bishkek-Naryn-Torugart road connecting Central Asia and China. The restoration of the Osh-Batken-Isfana road, which starts in the city of Osh, continues to the southwest and ends in the city of Isfana on the border with Tajikistan, will significantly provide access to the trade markets of South Asia. The Osh-Jalal Abad-Kok-Yangak and Balıkhchi-Bishkek-Lugovoye (Kazakhstan) routes connect with Russia through Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, respectively. They are expected to connect with Europe, Central Asia and China in connection with the Eurasian railway corridor.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that cooperation in the various fields listed above will make important contributions to the strengthening of the role of the Turkic world in global political and economic processes in the future. This is of exceptional importance in the context of regional and international stability, security and cooperation construction of the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway, the purpose of this project is to develop the Southern Corridor of the Eurasian transcontinental railway, which passes through the territory of Kyrgyzstan and connects the Iranian Gulf and the Mediterranean Sea. With the implementation of this project, the length of the road from East Asia to the Middle East and Southern Europe will decrease to 900 km, and the arrival time will decrease to 7-8 days. Currently, preparations are being made for the implementation of other energy and transport projects in Turkic-speaking countries. These projects, which are excellent examples of regional cooperation, bring progress and development to the people of the Turkic world.

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